

Supplementary Material

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Supplementary information is available on Kidney International's website.

Supplementary Figure 1. Coomassie blue-staining of urine proteins from vehicle- or STZ-treated control and cKOt mice. LMWP – low molecular weight proteins; ALB = albumin (65kDa). For all mice, 0.3% (vol) of 24-hour urine were loaded on an SDS-PAGE gel.

Supplementary Figure 2A. Masson's trichrome staining of kidney sections from vehicle- or STZ-treated control and cKOt mice.

Supplementary Figure 2B. Periodic acid Schiff (PAS) staining of kidney sections from vehicle- or STZ- treated control and cKOt mice.

Supplementary Figure 4. Capillary Western blot analysis of GLUD1 (panel A) and PCK1 (panel B) expression in kidneys of vehicle- or STZ-treated control and cKOt mice. The anti-GLUD1 and anti-PCK1 antibodies were from Abcam (ab166618 and ab70358, respectively). A protein normalization procedure (PN) was applied in each run through the fixation of a fluorophore (TAMRA) onto the proteins linked to the capillaries. It reflects the total protein loading in each capillary (panels C and D).

Supplementary Figure 5. Capillary Western blot analysis of GLUD1 (panel A) and PCK1 (panel B) expression in the liver of vehicle- or STZ- treated control and cKOt mice. The anti-GLUD1 and anti-PCK1 antibodies were from Abcam (ab166618 and ab70358, respectively). A protein normalization procedure (PN) was applied in each run through the fixation of a fluorophore (TAMRA) onto the proteins linked to the capillaries. It reflects the total protein loading in each capillary (panels C and D). Panels E and F: Western blot quantitation for GLUD1 and PCK1, respectively. Two-way ANOVA with Sidak's multiple comparisons test. † $p < 0.01$, ‡ $p < 0.001$.

Supplementary Table 1. Plasma chemistry in Vehicle- or STZ-injected Control and cKOt mice.

	Vehicle			STZ			Vehicle - STZ	
	Control (n=8)	cKOt (n=8)	<i>p</i> - <i>value</i>	Control (n=9)	cKOt (n=9)	<i>p</i> - <i>value</i>	Control <i>p</i> - <i>value</i>	cKOt <i>p</i> - <i>value</i>
Urea (mM)	7.79 ± 0.30	8.34 ± 0.28	<i>NS</i>	6.70 ± 0.17	7.57 ± 0.24	<i>0.03</i>	< <i>0.01</i>	<i>NS</i>
Osmolality (mOsm/kg H₂O)	331.9 ± 6.6	322 ± 9.7	<i>NS</i>	342.3 ± 8.1	362.0 ± 6.5	<i>NS</i>	<i>NS</i>	< <i>0.01</i>
Na⁺ (mM)	147.1 ± 1.6	146.1 ± 1.6	<i>NS</i>	143.1 ± 2.7	147.0 ± 1.2	<i>NS</i>	<i>NS</i>	<i>NS</i>
K⁺ (mM)	4.16 ± 0.13	4.63 ± 0.27	<i>NS</i>	4.47 ± 0.24	4.37 ± 0.18	<i>NS</i>	<i>NS</i>	<i>NS</i>
PO₄²⁻ (mM)	2.00 ± 0.12	2.39 ± 0.11	<i>NS</i>	2.15 ± 0.13	2.30 ± 0.14	<i>NS</i>	<i>NS</i>	<i>NS</i>
Ca²⁺ (mM)	2.09 ± 0.06	1.94 ± 0.08	<i>NS</i>	1.76 ± 0.16	1.96 ± 0.09	<i>NS</i>	<i>NS</i>	<i>NS</i>
Mg²⁺ (mM)	0.96 ± 0.05	1.04 ± 0.06	<i>NS</i>	0.98 ± 0.05	1.07 ± 0.04	<i>NS</i>	<i>NS</i>	<i>NS</i>
Creatinine (μM)	12.53 ± 0.54	14.04 ± 0.65	<i>NS</i>	17.52 ± 0.84	17.21 ± 0.78	<i>NS</i>	< <i>0.001</i>	< <i>0.01</i>
Urate (μM)	64.13 ± 9.95	38.13 ± 5.35	<i>NS</i>	61.00 ± 10.15	68.56 ± 11.26	<i>NS</i>	<i>NS</i>	<i>NS</i>
Aldosterone (pg/ml)	235.8 ± 48.7	260.3 ± 50.5	<i>NS</i>	392.0 ± 70.3	236.6 ± 38.1	<i>NS</i>	<i>NS</i>	<i>NS</i>